

ROLE OF COMPUTERS IN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract:

The purpose of the computer for Human Resource Managers is to improve the quality of the services they are offering. Computers upkeep us. As a manager we carry out our human resources responsibilities by performing a variety of time consuming jobs. A large amount of the work in the human resources office is clerical in nature. By using Information Technology, many of the routine jobs can be automated and the number of persons can be reduced for these tasks. In large organizations, one of the biggest problems is to upkeep the current data file. It has been proved that one of the supporting pillars which can contribute to the fulfillment of the personal policy is the usage of Information Technologies in Human Resource Management. Computers should be believed of as another human resources management tool, like a growth program, an assignment process which when used properly, can help us to maximize the quality of the products and services we offer.

Key Words: Human Resource Management, Information Technology, Services, Computer & Organization

Role of Computers in Human Resource Management:

Introduction:

Information Technology has great uses in almost all sorts of production areas. All these kinds of product manufacturers are trusting computers for automating their outdated processes. The computer technology has taken deep origins in every field nowadays. It is impossible for anyone to imagine a world without computer environment. In the management field, the computer plays a vital role directly or indirectly. At all the 3 levels of management i.e. at the operational level, middle level and high level, wide use of computers is made. Today, very few human resources departments are found without internal computer networks. This can be endorsed, in part, to the fast developments in computer technology. Hardware, in particular, desktop computers have reduced the cost and that has made these systems reasonable even for the smallest organizations.

Role of Computers in HR Functions:

The HR function consists of pursuing existing employee data which traditionally includes personal records, skills, abilities, activities and salary. To reduce the manual workload of these administrative activities, organizations began to electronically automate many of these processes by introducing specialized human resource management systems. HR executives rely on internal or external IT professionals to develop and maintain an integrated Human Resource Information System (HRIS). Human resource management systems facilitated gradually advanced administrative control of such systems. Other human resources functions such as recruitment, hiring, performance appraisals, compensation, benefits administration and training can all be done without paper. Running a business will definitely generate a lot of information, both related to the business and related to the organization's employees. The management needs to be able to use and secure this information in a system for a couple of different reasons. First, they don't want confidential information about the organization or employees getting into the wrong hands. Additionally, a human resource information software system is a wise choice because it will reduce the amount of paper generated, organize your data, streamline processes, and help your organization's bottom line. The HRIS system is an investment to an organization and is more than just a storage and organizational tool to contain confidential information about an organization's employees.

Human Resource Management Information Systems:

Briefly written as HRMS/HRIS, it refers to the systems and processes at the intersection of human resource management (HRM) and information technology. Today computer applications are merely thought as another management, which when used properly, helps an organization to enhance the quality of products and services it offers. The function of human resources (HR) departments is generally administrative and common to all organizations. Organizations may have formalized selection, evaluation, and payroll processes. Efficient and effective management of "human capital" progressed to an increasingly imperative and complex process.

Benefits:

- ✓ It makes an office paperless, i.e. because of these systems; there is now no need for notepads, post-notes or any day-planners.
- ✓ Increased storage efficiency
- ✓ Cost-effective
- ✓ Time saving
- ✓ Securing of data

Role of Computers in the Different Areas of HRM:

Payroll - Payroll is the sum of all financial records of salaries, wages, bonuses and deductions for an employee. In accounting, payroll refers to the amount paid to employees for services they provided during a certain period of time. The payroll management module has the basic task of automating the pay process in an organization. The outstanding benefit of Payroll Management System is its easy implementation. The Payroll Management System deals with the financial aspects of employee's salary, allowances, deductions, gross pay, net pay etc. and generation of pay-slips for a specific period. It has the following benefits that are briefly enlisted below:

- ✓ Manage Employee Information Efficiently.
- ✓ Define the emoluments, deductions, leave etc.
- ✓ Generate Pay-Slips
- ✓ Generate and Manage the Payroll Processes according to the Salary Structure assigned to the employee.
- ✓ Generation of reports related to employees and their tasks.
- ✓ Security Management

Benefits Administration - Benefits administration involves the creation and management of employee benefits, as well as providing a means for employees to be trained in understanding how the benefits work and what types of standards employees must meet in order to qualify for the benefits. This module helps provide a system for organizations to administer and track employee participation in benefits programs. These typically encompass insurance, compensation, profit sharing and retirement.

Training and Development – This module tracks employee profiles and schedules training events. It also manages the identification, responsibilities, authorities, and training and certification requirements for each employee in an easy-to-use environment. The system, normally called a "learning management system" (LMS) if a standalone product, allows HR to track education, qualifications and skills of the employees, as well as outlining what training courses, books, CDs, web based learning or materials are available to develop skills.

Recruitment - One way in which human resources has been significantly impacted by technology is in the area of recruiting. Before the Internet, HR recruiters had to rely on print publications, such as newspapers, to post jobs and get views for open positions. Other methods such as networking also were used, but HR recruiters did not have the ability to post a job in one or more locations and have millions of people see it all at once. Technology has made recruiting more efficient and in the hands of the right recruiter, more effective as well.

Employee Self-Service Module - The employee self-service module allows employees to query HR related data and perform some HR transactions over the system. Employees may query their attendance record from the system without asking the information from HR personnel. The module also lets supervisors approve over-time requests from their subordinates through the system without overloading the task on HR department. Many organizations have gone beyond the traditional functions and developed human resource management information systems, which support recruitment, selection, hiring, job placement, performance appraisals, employee benefit analysis, health, safety and security, while others integrate an outsourced applicant tracking system that encompasses a subset of the above. The time and attendance module keeps a track record of all the activities related to Human Resources and production of services and/or products. It is an advanced module that provides broad flexibility in data collection methods, labour distribution capabilities and data analysis features. Cost analysis and efficiency metrics are some secondary functions of this component of Human Resource Management Information Systems.

Performance Appraisal - This module evaluates and compares the job performance of an employee against the set target or other employees. Some applications of performance appraisal are compensation, performance improvement, promotions, termination, test validation etc. There are a number of potential benefits of organizational performance management conducting formal performance appraisals (PAs). There has been a general consensus in the belief that PAs lead to positive implications of organizations, so this module is also incorporated into the modern HR Management Systems.

Advantages:

The HR department has numerous benefits of this approach:

- ✓ Possession of single database of all employees in the company with all necessary information and opportunities for different reports.
- ✓ The ability to update databases in real time, on the basis of all changes, which is of extreme importance to regionally diversified companies.
- ✓ Elimination of paper forms that are much slower and with much higher probability of errors.
- ✓ Employees in HR department do not have to constantly refer to the instructions on working hours, because the application is configured according to existing guidelines, which have reduced delays and uncertainties.
- ✓ Reduction or elimination of unemployment in the system, which results in high reliability of data in the system.
- ✓ Increased employee satisfaction in HR department due to ease in execution of tasks.

- ✓ The ability to establish full control over internal migration of employees and the management of their talents.

Limitations:

While HR Management systems have countless advantages, they do have their downsides as well. Data Theft - With data theft on the rise, many companies are forced to improve their network security. And although they spend millions of dollars every year on securing these networks, the focus has largely been on securing the access to the network rather than protecting the information itself. Cost - Prices can range from \$40 to \$100 per user for companies with up to 50 employees and \$200 to \$300 per employee for larger companies. Installation, setup and consulting can cost as much as \$50,000. Difficulty of Analysis - Our system can contain so much data that we may find it difficult to analyze. We may need a separate analysis system just to sort the data into meaningful chunks. Although almost all HR managers understand the importance of HRIS, the general perception is that the organization can do without its establishment. Hence only large companies have started using HRIS to complement its HR activities. But HRIS would be very critical for organizations in the near future. This is because of a number of reasons.

- ✓ Large amount of data and information to be processed.
- ✓ Project based work environment.
- ✓ Employee empowerment.
- ✓ Increase of knowledge workers & associated information.
- ✓ Learning organization

The primary reason for delay in HRIS implementation in organizations is because of the fear psychosis created by "technology" and "IT" in the minds of senior management. They may not be very tech know-how and fear being left out. But trends are changing for the better as more and more organizations realize the importance of IT and technology. Major HRIS providers are concentrating on the small and middle range organizations as well as large organizations for their products. They are also coming up with very specific software modules, which would cater to any of their HR needs. Hence HRIS would soon be an integral part of HR activities in all organization.

Conclusion:

The applications of computers in human resources management has extended into areas imagined merely 2 decades back. With just a few keystrokes, or clicks on a mouse, organizations can instantly connect to sources of information that used to take weeks or months to access. Computers facilitate the storing and retrieving of employee records, policy information, and correspondence creating a show able paper trail. The vast majority of firms have made at least some of IT to transform their HR functions. In fact, within US corporations alone, IT now represents the single largest capital expenditure, accounting for almost one-third of all capital investment. Recently, the computers have lowered the employee training costs through interactive training programmes, implementations and hands-on training opportunities. Generally, traditional HRM functions are common to all organizations. They consist of tracking data regarding personal histories, family details, skills, capabilities, experiences, pay, benefits and grievances. Performance of these functions is increasingly complex, that must be performed at the lowest possible cost and also at a fast rate, which pose increased challenges for HR professionals. Organizations have started to automate these functions by introducing HRIS technology. A Human Resources Information System is a system that lets you keep track of all your employees and information about them. It is usually done in a database or, more often, in a series of interrelated databases. Hence, development of client-server HRIS enables HR executives to assume responsibility and ownership of their systems. The current pressures and issues affecting library and information services in all sectors are well known and have been documented in numerous articles and reports over the past decade. Human resources information systems have evolved since the 1980s from relatively simple computer applications to virtual treasuries of sophisticated human resources information and processes. HRIS also is the name of the human resources discipline for HRIS specialists and other human resources professionals involved in the technology for employment and personnel matters.

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